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A REVIEW ON INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY CHALLENGES OF LAND SECTOR IN ETHIOPIA AND THE WAY FORWARD

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Abstract

The existence of vibrant, effective, and functional institutions is the backbone for the realization of development aspirations and prosperity of societies. Nevertheless, most developing countries institutions lack the required capacity to effectively discharge their vested responsibilities. This ultimately hinders the nations development. This article is aimed at pinpointing the major challenges affecting the capacity of institutions and deterring effective service delivery and thereby suggesting the way forward. To this end, different theoretical and empirical works conducted on the Ethiopian context were reviewed. The review results illustrate employees' incompetence and imbalance at different levels of government agencies in budgetary allocation and distribution which in turn is affecting the degree of transparency, accountability, and responsiveness. Besides, the review also identified the existence of serious gap in making public institutions responsive to the demands of the citizenry. Aimed at establishing vibrant and effective institutions, the authors among others, suggested building linkage, good relationship, and synergy among different public and private organizations. Furthermore, considering human capital development as a cornerstone for institutional capacity building, it requires providing demand-driven and quality-oriented practical training for land sector employees and stakeholders to bridge the existing capacity deficit.

Keywords: Institutions, capacity, institutional capacity, challenges, way forward

Introduction and Justification

As articulated in the ten-year national plan, Ethiopia as a nation is aspiring to become one of the middle-income countries in the world. Without doubt, realizing the aspiration significantly depends on the existence of strong, independent, and effective institutions. That is why the issue of institutional capacity development has been given an increasing attention. An enhanced institutional capacity results in the improvement of public sector performance and operational efficiency (Domorenok, Graziano, & Polverari, 2021). Such institutional competence is required to deliver efficient and effective services (Emiru, 2022). Ensuring institutional competence, on the other hand, necessitates the interaction and collaboration between public and private sector and professionals (Belachew & Aytenfisu, 2010; Emiru, 2022).

Enabling full citizens control over public institutions and agencies is one of the fundamental pre-requisites in democracy (Agüero, 2021). Thus, there is a need to ensure the right fit between citizens' demand and government capacity (Droic & Keiser, 2021; Williams, 2020). This is mainly attributed to the fact that in democratic societies, government is elected periodically by citizens and to have any chance for re-election, they need to faithfully, diligently, and adequately address the needs and interests of the electorate using available resources.

In most of the developing countries, including Ethiopia, where the democratization process is at its infant stage, how government are sensitive and responsive to the citizens' demand is unclear and questionable. Besides, most of the researches within the public sector emphasizes the issue of efficiency and effectiveness with the intention of improving public sector performance and productivity, and thus failed to sufficiently address how institutions are capable to deliver efficient services and the kind of specific challenge they are facing rather than identifying in generic terms the existence of institutional capacity deficit which makes this review imperative and timely.

There are ample documented evidences that indicate situations in public institutions that tend to respond to the preferences of the state authorities, international donors, or foreign-funded NGOs that provide the necessary resources instead of public demands (Hydén & Samuel, 2015). Consequently, citizens would be forced to regard elected government officials as being insufficiently responsive as their political representatives (Bourgon, 2007). Little is known regarding the interface between citizen and state at the local level in Sub-Saharan Africa (Bratton, 2010). This is partly due to the existence of meager empirical studies.

Though the Government of Ethiopia has made several endeavors to build responsive and capable public institutions in the last three decades, there are still various bottlenecks hindering the process which include the capacity deficit, inefficiently designed and implemented administrative decentralization schemes, and inappropriate monitoring system among others. If this problem is not thoroughly examined and possible policy options provided, it has the potential to negatively impact on efficient and effective service provision and the developmental aspirations of the country. With this in mind, the article is aimed at investigating the challenges facing land sector institutions in Ethiopia with the ultimate purpose of suggesting the way forward.

Conceptualizing Institutional Capacity and Its Link with Good Governance

According to UNDP (2007), capacity is the ability of individuals, institutions, and societies to perform functions properly, mitigate problems, and set and realize goals and objectives sustainably. It also deals with individuals, organizations, and societies' ability to manage their affairs successfully (Vallejo & Wehn, 2016; Emiru, 2022). Furthermore, it enables organizations to function in a strategic, resilient, and autonomous manner (Kaplan, 2007). In other words, capacity is about empowerment which allows individuals, groups, and organizations to build their self-awareness, to grow, and diversify their skills (Blinkerhoff, 2007). From the systems phenomenon, capacity requires multiple interactions involving attitudes, resources, strategies, structures, skills, and communication. Hence, it has technical, organizational, and social aspects (OECD, 2006). It, therefore, goes that capacity is the cumulative effect of individual competencies and contributions, as well as collective capabilities, from the viewpoint of an organization (Baser & Morgan, 2008; Simba, Mukose, & Bazeyo, 2014).

Capacity is the ability of individuals or groups and organizations to perform the functions effectively, efficiently, and sustainably; whereas capacity building is an evidence-driven process of strengthening the abilities of individuals, organizations, and systems to perform core functions sustainably, and to continue to improve and develop over the time (Whyte, 2004). As per these conceptualization, capacity development comprises of up-grading individuals, groups, and population's way of performing entrusted tasks as well as reforming, transforming, and modernizing the entire working process and living environment for new leadership or for service renders (OECD, 2006).

In order to effectively formulate and implement public policies, government institutions, among others, depends on the effectiveness, and independence from direct and indirect political pressure. Moreover, the quality of policy formulation and implementation also depends on government commitment. Consequently, capacity building is required for creating incentives for lower level implementers to undertake actions that

enhance capacities effectively. It is equally essential to provide support and guidance as they build skills in decision making, planning, resource mobilization and management, communication and coordination, and conflict resolution.

To develop the capability of people, as individuals and as a group, and to properly discharge their responsibilities, the leadership need both skills and knowledge. Precisely, the ability to analyze and challenge information received from the executive, including skills in financial management and the ability to recognize when outside expert advice is needed is required. They also need to be updated regularly to equip themselves to properly respond to changing circumstances (Parida, Pesämaa, Wincent, & Westerberg, 2017).

Weak human power competencies and institutional capabilities hinder the realization of good governance and thus require comprehensive intervention. According to DFID (2010), there are five core capabilities that enable an organization and individual to perform and survive that can help to identify capacity strengths or weaknesses and to monitor the change over time. These include the capability to commit and engage; the capability to carry out technical, service delivery, and logical tasks; capability to relate and attract resources and support; capability to adapt and self-awareness, as well as the capability to balance diversity and coherence (Baser & Morgan, 2008).

Capacity is a combination of institutions and respective organizations; commitment and vision of leadership; financial and material resources; skilled human resources (Baser & Morgan, 2008; Farrell & Coburn, 2016; Byungura, Hansson, Masengesho, & Karunaratne, 2016); and a process of unleashing, strengthening, creating, adapting and maintaining capacity overtime (OECD, 2006; Mulubiran, 2012). It further requires institutional adjustments, free access to information, capacity-building, and political commitment (WPSR, 2015). Therefore, in the absence of the required capacity, government institutions cannot able to realize the effective functioning of good governance principles in the public sector.

Furthermore, lack of commitment on the part of leadership and employees is a challenge that deters the realization of good governance in public sectors (Byarugaba, Bagiire, & Bagorogoza, 2012; Abakose & Abagojam, Good Governance Practices and Public Service Delivery in Jimma Town, Ethiopia, 2021). This is why effective leadership is essential for successfully realizing good governance efforts. This also requires an increasing political commitment to sustainable human development, which includes assistance for training in planning and implementation, building national competencies and developing approaches to public-private partnerships (Abebaw, 2021).

The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) has concentrated on strengthening management in three areas that are vital to sustainable human development - reform of the civil service, economic and financial management, and urban management. This is because, leadership capacity enhancement programs must be conceived and implemented with the aim of making leaders capable of effectively addressing the key challenges facing the sectors (Issa & David, 2012; Byarugaba, Bagiire, & Bagorogoza, 2012; Nega, Jemberu, & Asress, 2020).

From the perspective of service delivery, governance can be understood as the set of incentives, accountability arrangements, and rules that affect the way key actors including policy makers, organizations and their managers and staff are held accountable for their behaviours and ability to deliver high-quality services with efficiency and responsiveness (Mdee & Thorley, 2016). In this discussion, the term ‘policy makers’ refers to the high-level elected officials or civil servants responsible for implementing legislative and regulatory responsibilities, while providers are the program managers, local officials, and others involved in the administration and delivery of services, as well as frontline service providers, such as doctors, teachers, and social workers, who interact directly with the public (Ringold, Holla, Koziol, & Srinivasan, 2012).

To strengthen the accountability system, it requires vibrant institutions and proper interactions among policy makers and politicians, service providers, and citizens (Gacitúa-Marió, Norton, & Moreno, 2009). Citizens and beneficiaries of services can affect the latter social through their voice and by the behaviour of service providers, i.e. through client power. To exert this influence, they need access to information and capacity to translate into concrete action. Expanding opportunities for using information also involves building the capacity of users to understand and leverage information for action and opening channels to use it. Medias and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) are also an important actor’s in facilitating access to information and

transforming individual efforts to collective power to make service providers and policy makers accountable for their actions and deeds (Gacitúa-Marió, Norton, & Georgieva, 2009).

Institutional Capacity Challenges in Ethiopia

Scholars underscored that institutional capacity determines economic performance and socio-economic development (Gilmer, 2016). On the other hand, building vibrant and well-functioning institutions calls for leadership and human capital development (Mengesha & Singh, 2022; Chang, 2010; Arogundade, Mduzuzi, Eita, & Elliott, 2022; Bouckaert, Peters, & Verhoest, 2010).

Evidence from various nations illustrates that sufficient institutional capacity results in reducing poverty (IMF, 2022; Arogundade, Mduzuzi, Eita, & Elliott, 2022). Importantly, sound institutional capacity improves equitable and efficient provision of quality-oriented and timely public goods and services such as health, education, water, and roads (Slade & JenniferCarter, 2016); and ensures successful land administration system as well enhance governance (Emiru, 2022). The presence of vivid institutional capacity also improve evidence-based policy making and the effectiveness of its implementation (Doshmangi, et al., 2022; Čolić, Milić, & Petrić, 2021), and contributes towards success of developmental projects implementation (Di-Maró, Evans, Khemani, & Scot, 2021).

In the Ethiopian context, particularly in the land sector, there is a lack of transparency and accountability (Emiru, 2022; Belachew & Aytenu, 2010; Desalegn & Solomon, 2021). Besides, absence of explicitly articulated strategies to build capacity is obstructing proper land service delivery (Ragasa, et al., 2021). Furthermore, there is pervasive and widespread systemic corruption and abuse of power coupled by service delivery delays (Desalegn & Solomon, 2021). Again, costly and bureaucratic procedures, lack of sufficient resources, poorly designed and implemented legal frameworks, and improper organizational structure are also constitute the challenge (Desalegn & Solomon, 2021; Shiferaw, 2017). This challenges are mainly attributable to lack of intergovernmental or stakeholders collaboration and coordination, inequitable allocation of infrastructure across various regions as well inadequate political commitment (Desalegn & Solomon, 2021). There is also a tendency of imitating the systems and knowledge of developed nations by ignoring the existing capabilities. This approach, which the researchers argues as an 'old approach', is problematic not only because it fails to embrace indigenous knowledge and capabilities, but also instills dependency syndrome (Abebaw, 2021; Byarugaba, Bagiire, & Bagorogoza, 2012).

Tadesse (2013) assessed public service delivery and governance system taking Beneshangul Gumuz Regional State as a case study. The study specifically examined the capacity and role of different actors in ensuring good governance. The research revealed that, while the private firms play a leading role among the non-state actors, the role of the public still remains negligible. To put it differently, the involvement of the public in the different platforms is inadequate. Besides, agencies at different levels in the region are less responsive to public demands. The researcher identified that limited human resource capacity and political interference are the main reasons contributing to the problem. Likewise, the absence of an appropriate voicing mechanism and non-existent media coverage had adversely affected public responsiveness.

The author also articulated the presence of staff incompetence and imbalance between higher and lower level agencies in budgetary allocation which in turn negatively affected the level of transparency, responsiveness, voicing, and accountability. Yet, he argued that building capacity alone is not sufficient to improve performance. Instead, there is a need to formulate policies for empowering the public to enable them to raise their voice and to hold service providers accountable in order to make the service a demand-driven one.

Charu (2016) has undertaken a study on solid waste management in Addis Ababa with the aim of discovering a new approach to waste management system. The scholar established the existence of gap in rules, regulations, and policies officially adopted to improve solid waste management system. Consequently, he concluded that the policies are designed and adopted to suit governments own interest and agenda and thus, ultimately, failed to improve the management of solid waste in Addis Ababa.

Sungena, Serbeh-Yiadom and Asfaw (2014) conducted an empirical study primarily aimed at evaluating the performance of urban land service delivery against the principles of good urban land governance under the

theme ‘strengthening good governance in urban land management in Ethiopia’. To this end, the researchers used descriptive research design and found out that urban land service delivery in Hawassa city administration is languishing with lack of transparency and accountability. Besides, they have also established that urban land service delivery is inequitable, inefficient, ineffective, and ill-functioning which in turn is negatively contributing towards the overall development of the city. On the basis of their research findings, they suggested the city needs to build a system that will promote popular participation, transparency, equity, accountability, and thus potentially meet good governance objectives in land management and development. Furthermore, effective capacity-building measures were also proposed to improve ineffective and inefficient land service delivery system of the city administration. In support of this, it’s empirically established the processes of regularization of land ownership by the poor haven’t been practiced transparently and in most cases contradicts with a societal norms and values (Fraol, Dagnachew, & Liku, 2021). The processes and systems of land administration are also found to be discriminatory (Solomon, Vries, & Gebeyehu, 2020).

Berhanu (2015) also conducted his doctoral dissertation on ‘urban cadastre for urban land governance’ employing different methods consisting of literature reviews and case studies. The dissertation was ultimately targeted to develop an integrated conceptual model to understand urban land governance. Findings of the research demonstrates that there had been tenure insecurity, lack of information access, inequity of land distribution, as well as the presence of informal settlements which support informal land market. It’s also confirmed that there is weak local government capacity, lack of transparency, and rent-seeking behaviors.

Esayas Engida Dube examined urban planning and land management challenges in emerging towns of Ethiopia by taking Arba Minch as a case. He aimed at identifying land management challenges and assessing whether the prepared master plan for the town had realized its intended objectives. To that end, 340 households were selected and participated using systematic sampling technique. Besides, individuals who directly participate in the planning and management of urban land were addressed through key informant interviews. Several available policies, plans, and directives associated with urban land planning and management were also reviewed. The empirical work revealed that the town was using an out-dated land information management system (Dube, 2013). Though the master plan was being implemented, it failed to sufficiently realize its intended target. According to the finding, this is mainly attributed to the presence of widespread corruption, informal land acquisitions, land related conflicts, weak and ineffective institutional framework, as well as the application of a top-down approach to planning. Likewise, problem in effectively implementing the existing land policies and proclamations, technical and capacity deficiency, attitudinal problems, and weak coordination among governmental bodies and other stakeholders are identified as the major challenges hindering the effectiveness of land management system in Ethiopia (Dereje & Dagneu, 2020; Lindner, 2014).

A descriptive survey was conducted by Mhrtey Adisalem Tikue on Naeder Adet Woreda of Tigray Regional State to evaluate the performance of good governance specifically emphasizing on transparency and responsiveness in land administration. The study indicates that some efforts are in place to improve the performance service delivery (Tikue, 2016). The outcome of the study shows lack of transparency, absence of clear service standards, attitudinal problems, and poor documentations are the major impediments to ensure responsiveness in the Woreda. In general, most studies attest deficient institutional capacity to that lack of good governance in land administration, lack of qualified manpower, inadequate resource allocation, weak coordination among stakeholders and implementation capacity and public awareness, absence of strong and effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, unclear responsibility mechanism, bureaucratic complexities, as well as presence of corruption (Gemedra, Abebe, & Cirella, 2020; Tikue, 2016; Dereje & Dagneu, 2020; Nebere, Tolossa, & Bantide, 2021; Tayiba, 2013; Abebaw, 2021; Temesgen, 2020; Lindner, 2014). Furthermore, absence of comprehensive land policy, lack of effective land administration institutions, lack of transparency and standardized valuation and compensation methods, and land grabbing are further exacerbating land governance in Ethiopia (Temesgen, 2020).

Berhanu, Jaap, and Rohan (2015) further assessed land administration and governance in Ethiopian cities from the perspective of urban land management policy. For the purpose, they employed exploratory case study design. The cases were analysed using SWOT technique. The SWOT analysis result indicates that land

administration and governance in Ethiopia is largely weak and surrounded by growing number of weaknesses and threats. Specifically, lack of working land policy, lack of coordination among existing institutions, lack of community participation, lack of transparency, weak implementation capacity, and weak monitoring systems were investigated as the major shortcomings in land administration and governance of studied cases. Besides, poor participation during planning and decision-making process and over-emphasizing on the short-term gains instead of strategically focusing on the long term-term benefits is adversely affecting the sustainability of land management practices (Nebere, Tolossa, & Bantide, 2021).

Melese (2016) assessed the practices and challenges of land management and development in Addis Ababa focusing on Yeka sub-city administration by applying good governance principles. The author established the processes of managing and developing land services is not transparent. Besides, it was also found the existence of weak citizens' participation and unequal treatment of customers. Consequently, the service users are dissatisfied with the land management and development practices (Melese, 2016). The Ethiopian Urbanization Report compiled by the World Bank in 2016 also revealed that urban land governance capacity to develop a comprehensive land asset and enhance own revenue sources is generally weak. Similarly, the national report of Ethiopian Ministry of Construction and Urban Development illustrates that the overall system of governance of land management and development in Ethiopia has some substantial structural pitfalls as there is excessive over-regulation in addition to the reliance on top-down approach which left local governments to have no-control over land management and development parameters. Similarly, complexity in institutional arrangements of land administration, administrative capacity shortfall, overlapping and duplicated mandates, and pitfalls in employees commitment were identified as the major challenges to providing proper land services to the customers (Ketema, 2020).

Challenges of Urban Land Service Delivery Reforms in Ethiopia

Although there are reforms which were undertaken in Ethiopia with the objective of improving the quality of land services and increase public satisfaction, there are still challenges that continue to deter the efficient, effective, and responsive land service delivery. In this sub-section, an effort is made to review and present the major challenges affecting the delivery of quality land services.

According to Brown (2012), one problem is the tendency to view the existence of comprehensive solutions which address all land service delivery associated challenges across the country. Yet, the reality calls for the application of various approaches, processes, and tools in a tandem rather than sequential manner if organizational performance is to be improved in a sustainable way. This is why all components of reform should be implemented in an integrated way. Brown, however, noted that such an approach has not been practiced in Ethiopia. If it had, it is conceivable that the reform programs might have been brought a much better result in improving the quality of land service delivery.

To make accountability mechanisms effective and improve service delivery, Garcia and Kumar (2008) noted the need to match delegation of responsibilities with adequate finance, especially at a local government level. Besides, expenditure assignments of the different levels of government need to be accurately, fully, and clearly defined. They found that this does not yet happened to a sufficient degree in Ethiopia. Lack of clear assignments can lead to duplication of effort and lack of coordination. It also makes it difficult to assign roles and budgets in order to meet functional objectives. There is also a gap in legal framework that harmonize the relationship among different levels regarding what is expected from them, how they are supposed to complement each other, or how each level is supposed to complement.

The World Bank Report of 2014 also illustrates that many of Ethiopian Woredas have been limited by the lack of adequate staff to deal with the challenge of improving service provision. The also noted that there is high vacant position in public sector. More worryingly, turnover and scarcity of staff are high in professional and technical areas where many staffs are leaving away from public sectors. Besides, though strategic personnel management and compensation policies of service providers are key to the success of service delivery reforms as appropriate strategies to motivate and retain professional staffs, strategic personnel management is the least developed area in the public sector. Thus, this challenge has to be urgently addressed to improve the quality and performance of service provision.

In general, lack of quality staff and organizational structure (Hailu & Shifare, 2019), inefficient and ineffective operation of institutions (Beshah & Kitaw, 2014; Ali, Debela, & Bamud, 2017), low quality of service provisions (Bedasso, 2017; Hailu & Shifare, 2019; Tadesse, 2019), the problem of sustainability and implementation capacities of organizations (Yitbarek, et al., 2021), deficiencies in capacity building initiatives (Abagissa, 2019; Feleke, 2014), disparity in efficiency and implementation capacity among organizational units, attitudinal problems, poor participation of the citizens on prioritization and decision-making (Abagissa, 2019; Hailu & Shifare, 2019; Abakose & Abagojam, Good Governance Practices and Public Service Delivery in Jimma Town, Ethiopia, 2021), lack of competence and commitment (Abagissa, 2019; Tadesse, 2019), weak accountability and responsiveness systems (Haile, 2018; Teshome, Belete, Gizaw, & Mengiste, 2020) are identified as the major challenges and constraints that are prevalent in most public sector institutions.

Irresponsible Land Institutions as a Major Challenge

Responsiveness refers to “the willingness of leaders to register the preferences of constituents, that is, by paying attention to their requests and complaints” (Bratton, 2010, p. 3). It deals with “the effort that is made by a government agency to provide helpful, expeditious service to the public” (Friedman, 2009, p. 1). Responsiveness is also concerned with ensuring that clients are served helpfully and responsibly by government agencies and officials. Besides, it requires ensuring that every citizen have an access to governmental services that they want and entitled to have and involving citizens in policy-making (Friedman, 2009; Abidin, Singaravelloo, & Azizan, 2018). It requires treating the clients cooperatively and respectfully in addressing their queries. For instance, when a client enters a government facility and asks for help, the front-line service provider must listen to him and come to understand what need the client is expressing. Then, the service provider should make an effort to connect the client with the service or assistance to which he is entitled.

According to the prominent philosophic Jean Jacques Rousseau responsiveness is a “social contract” between citizens and their government. He explains that, when people establish a government, they are giving up some of the rights and freedoms that they would otherwise have for example, the right to drive in the left lane if they feel like it in exchange for benefits that they value more, such as the protection of their own safety and property and the expectation of greater prosperity. In general, it’s apparent that government agencies are an instrument to serve the people who established government for their benefit (Friedman, 2009; Bourgon, 2007; Drolc & Keiser, 2021).

To make public institutions more responsive to the demands of the citizenry, agencies need to ensure that their services are accessible to the needy (Benequista, 2010). This can be done, for instance, through establishing branch offices in places that are conveniently located for public access. Besides, public institutions can able to ensure that by making their communications comprehensible. Furthermore, resolving the problems of clients on spot is vital to warrant responsiveness. Involvement of citizens in associations has been an effective way of strengthening notions of citizenship and citizen engagement, which can contribute to more responsive states.

Within a public sector, providing timely response is a critical ingredient to ensure public confidence and trust which simultaneously leads to improving the quality of work and enhance satisfaction among the public (Abidin, Singaravelloo, & Azizan, 2018; Arnold, 2012; Bouckaert & Walle, 2003). As a result, public or bureaucratic agencies should respond to the desires, expectations, and aspirations of the society. This is particularly important since there is a strong positive association between responsiveness and public trust (Abidin, Singaravelloo, & Azizan, 2018). Consequently, governments at different levels need to build a responsive system to gain highly demanded trust from the general public (Abidin, Singaravelloo, & Azizan, 2018; Cleary, 2007; Bouckaert & Walle, 2003; West & Raso, 2013).

Different levels of governments in Ethiopia have limited technical capacities (Miruts, 2014). Besides, in most cases, their operations have been oriented more to top-down mandates rather than bottom-up demands. Importantly, government entities have rarely attained responsibility, accountability, and responsiveness in their different undertaking despite of various reform efforts undertaken to this end. This paper, therefore,

centrally argues building responsive, accountable, and transparent government entities at different levels is an important prerequisite to create a prosperous and developed nation.

Responsiveness calls for providing what customers' needs and wants at an appropriate cost. Besides, it requires continuous improvement of the existing services and development of new ones to satisfy customers. Moreover, allowing customers to exercise their rights and choices and making sure that they have sufficient quality and amount of information is a prerequisite.

The Way Forward

Building linkage, good relationship, and synergy among different public and private organizations is required to enhance their respective capacities. To this end, using the Public Private Partnership initiative presented by the government aimed at sharing resources, information, and capabilities as well as deterring challenges through collective actions is essential.

Undoubtedly human capital development is the cornerstone for building and developing vibrant institutions. As a result, the Government of Ethiopia needs to shift the focus from quantity to quality as the review identified the existence of employees' incompetence at different levels of government agencies. Specifically, to produce well-equipped and competent graduates who can be future employees, the educational policy has to be quality-oriented and demand-driven.

To establish good governance in the context of land management, it needs to design and implement a sound and coherent approach of capacity development which can promote and guide sustainable land management through institutional performance. Decisions so as to what should be done to address the problems go actually beyond the reach of individuals, and therefore, it requires an integrated approach including good governance mechanism and capacity development both at an individual and institutional level to ensure efficient and effective land service delivery.

Overall, we researchers believe that through properly implementing the suggested policy options, the country can improve its institutional capacity to better manage macroeconomic, political, and social issues and realize its developmental aspirations.

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